

Biopharmaceutical improvement of praziquantel by interaction with montmorillonite and sepiolite

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ABSTRACT

Praziquantel is the drug of first choice for the treatment of the human schistosomiasis. It is administered orally, requiring high doses to overcome adverse biopharmaceutical properties, including high lipophilia and intense hepatic first pass metabolism. According to its biopharmaceutical profile, praziquantel has very low water solubility and high permeability. Therefore, dissolution is the limiting factor for absorption in the gastrointestinal tract. Improvement of the aqueous solubility of the drug would reduce the currently high oral doses. Meanwhile, montmorillonite and sepiolite are clay minerals, with a high adsorption and swelling properties, potentially useful as a low-cost nanocarrier to design praziquantel delivery systems. In this work, the interactions between the drug and clay minerals are studied experimentally, with the aim of improving the biopharmaceutical profile of the drug. The results showed the effective loading of the drug in the clay minerals as well as the significant increase of the dissolution rate and the dissolved amount of praziquantel, potentially improving the bioavailability of the drug.

1. Introduction

Clay minerals, in particular montmorillonite and sepiolite, are widely used pharmaceutical excipients in different pharmaceutical dosage forms, designed for oral and topical administration (López-Galindo and Viseras, 2004; Viseras et al., 2010). Besides their classic pharmaceutical uses, clay minerals may be effectively used in the development of modified drug delivery systems (Aguzzi et al., 2007; Viseras et al., 2010).

Montmorillonite is a dioctahedral 2:1 phyllosilicate with one octahedral sheet and two tetrahedral sheets (T:O:T). An interlayer nanospace exists between each triple-sheet-layer. These layers have isomorphic substitutions of Si⁴⁺ by Al³⁺ in the tetrahedral sheet and Al³⁺ by Mg²⁺ in the octahedral layer. An important part of the physicochemical properties of montmorillonite depends on the isomorphic substitutions that confer a negative residual charge compensated by cations in the interlayer space. These interlayer spaces represent about 90% of the mineral total surface and are accessible to water molecules and other compounds, yielding a high adsorption capacity for polar molecules (Bergaya and Lagaly, 2006; Aguzzi et al., 2007).

On the other hand, sepiolite is a non-planar phyllosilicate with fibrous morphology. The basal oxygen layer is continuous but the apical

oxygens undergo a periodic inversion every 8 octahedral positions. This inversion causes a discontinuous octahedral layer forming long channels, where the water and organic molecules can be adsorbed (Guggenheim et al., 2006).

Because of their high adsorption and cation exchange capacities, both montmorillonite and sepiolite are peculiar nanostructured material. These solids can retain organic molecules in their structures and after administration release the retained active compounds under controlled conditions, being good candidates for the design of modified delivery systems of several drugs (Viseras et al., 2010). Besides the above mentioned clay minerals, halloysite nanotubes have been also exploited as nanocarriers for several applications (Massaro et al., 2016; Makaremi et al., 2017).

Praziquantel is the drug of choice for an extended parasitic disease, schistosomiasis that it is a parasitic disease caused by *Schistosoma*. The infection is caused by the parasite penetration through the skin of individuals, in contact with contaminated water. It is widely extended, mainly in at least 74 developing countries, in the tropics and subtropics (Chitsulo et al., 2000) and it affects 250 million people approximately, causing over half a million of deaths every year (Steinmann et al., 2006). Behind of malaria, the Schistosomiasis is the second of the most prevalent diseases that affects African children (WHO, 2017).

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Fig. 1. XRPD patterns of the studied samples.

Fig. 2. DSC profiles of the studied samples.

The prevention of the Schistosomiasis is difficult and there is no effective vaccine against the disease. Praziquantel is the most used drug for the treatment of Schistosomiasis (WHO, 2017). However, its extensive use and the lack of compliance during the treatment is causing drug resistance (Wang et al., 2012).

Praziquantel has a chiral center and only the R(-)-enantiomer possesses anthelmintic activity (Andrews, 1985) even if the actual treatments use a racemic mixture. It is classified in Class II in Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS) (FDA, 2017; González-Esquivel et al., 2005), due to its low aqueous solubility and high permeability, and has low absorption in the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) (Amidon et al., 1995). For these reasons, high oral doses are required to treat schistosomiasis. The interaction of praziquantel with montmorillonite in aqueous medium was studied by El-Feky et al. (2015). However, the resultant interaction products did not improve *in vitro* dissolution rates neither *in vivo* absorption rates. Probably, as a result of

the presence of water molecules in the interlayer space of the montmorillonite, the entry of praziquantel was hindered and the drug was only absorbed on the external surface, resulting in the absence of relevant biopharmaceutical improvements.

With these premises, aim of this work was to obtain praziquantel/clay mineral interaction products in absence of water as a strategy to improve the effective entrapment of the drug molecules. The potential increase in praziquantel solubility was a rational approach to the improvement of drug bioavailability.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Praziquantel (PZQ) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich (S). Ethanol of 99% of purity was used as solvent. Purified pharmaceutical degree

Fig. 3. TGA profiles of the studied samples.

Montmorillonite (Veegum HS®, VHS) was purchased from Vanderbilt Company (USA). The Sepiolite samples from Vicálvaro (Madrid) (SEP) were kindly gifted by TOLSA (S). These solids were used without any pretreatment and were characterized elsewhere (Torres-Rufz et al., 1994; Viseras and López-Galindo, 1999; Aguzzi et al., 2005).

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Preparation of praziquantel/clay minerals interaction products

Clay powders were dispersed in 100 mL of ethanolic solution of PZQ under magnetic stirring at room temperature for 24 h, in such way that the clay/drug ratio was 5:1 w/w in order to ensure complete interaction between the components. After 24 h, the solvent was evaporated at 40 °C by means a rotary evaporator (Buchi® R II, CH) and the solid residue (PZQ-VHS or PZQ-SEP prepared with VHS or SEP, respectively) was stored in a desiccator at room temperature with freshly activated silica-gel grafted with a moisture indicator of Co salt.

2.2.2. X-ray diffraction

Powder X-ray diffraction was performed with a Philips®X-Pert diffractometer with the CuK α wavelength. The information of diffraction was analyzed using XPOWDER® software (Martín-Ramos, 2005).

2.2.3. Thermal analysis

Differential Scanning Calorimetric analysis (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) were performed with a Mettler Toledo mod. TGA/DSC1 calorimeter, equipped with sensor and FRS5 microbalance (precision 0.1 μ g) and FP89 software package, using a heating rate of 5 °C/min in the 30–400 °C temperature range for TGA and DSC runs and a rate of 2 °C/min for additional specific DSC runs. Nitrogen was used as purge gas in DSC under flows of 100 and 15 mL/min.

2.2.4. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Microphotographs of the samples were performed using a Hitachi S-510 scanning electron microscope (voltage 25 kV, secondary electron images) (Hitachi Scientific Instruments Ltd., Tokyo, Japan). The samples were mounted on adhesive paper, fixed with colloidal gold and metallized with gold in two orientations (20–30°). The images were captured digitally using the program ScanVision, Version 1.2.

2.2.5. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) and Raman spectroscopies

FTIR spectra were recorded in the range 4000–600 cm^{-1} with a 0.5 cm^{-1} resolution and a well-plate sampler (JASCO 6200

spectrophotometer with Spectra Manager II software). Raman spectra were recorded in the range 3500–800 cm^{-1} with a 6.48 cm^{-1} resolution using a Micro-Raman dispersive JASCO NRS-5100 spectrophotometer, with laser light source VIS-NIR with red diode at 785 nm with 500 mW of power (TorsanaStarbright) and refrigeration by air and a KnowItAll JASCO Edition for Raman software.

2.2.6. In vitro release studies

Hard gelatine capsules containing 600 mg of each PZQ, PZQ-VHS and PZQ-SEP, in which 100 mg correspond to PZQ, were prepared. Similarly, hard gelatine capsules containing 100 mg of PZQ were elaborated as reference. The capsules were subjected to *in vitro* release studies following the European Pharmacopoeia procedure for dissolution test of solid oral dosage forms. Experiments were carried out using European Pharmacopoeia apparatus 2 with sinkers (Sotax AT7, CH) at 150 rpm, 37 °C, 1 L of dissolution medium (no sink conditions). Two dissolution media were used: i) HCl 0.001 M simulating the stomach physiological fluid; and ii) a simulated intestinal fluid (pH = 6.8) (SIF) without enzymes. At established time intervals, samples of dissolution medium (5 mL) were withdrawn, filtered through 0.45 μ m Millipore® (S) membranes and the amount of drug dissolved measured by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), using a 1260 Infinity II Agilent equipment (G) with quaternary pump, autosampler, column oven and UV-VIS diode-array spectrophotometer. The stationary phase was a column Kromasyl® C18, 5 μ m, 250 \times 4.6 mm (Teknokroma, S) and the mobile phase was a mixture of H₂O and CH₃CN (35:65 v/v). The flow rate was set at 0.8 mL/min with an injection volume of 10 μ L. A detector with a wavelength of 225 nm was used and the run time for each analysis was 5 min. Data were recorded and analyzed by using LC Open LAB HPLC 1260 software (Agilent, G). The analytical method was linear in the concentration range 10–50 mg/L of PZQ in both media, resulting in correlation coefficients of 0.9994 (HCl 0.001 M) and 0.9992 (SIF).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. X-ray diffraction

The powder XRD patterns of raw components and interaction products are shown in Fig. 1. PZQ showed the most intense reflection at around 16.5° 2 θ and other intense reflections at approximately 8.0°, 19.1° and 23.3° 2 θ according with that previously reported (El-Subbagh and Al-Badr, 1998). After interaction with the clay minerals, complete

Fig. 4. SEM microphotographs of PZQ (A–B), VHS (C–D), PZQ-VHS (E–F) and PZQ-SEP (G–H).

absence of drug reflections was probably due to a loss of crystallinity of PZQ. In previous works a similar behavior of PZQ was observed in the formation of a solid dispersion with PVP (polyvinylpyrrolidone) (De la Torre et al., 1999) and with sodium starch glycolate (Chaud et al., 2013).

As a result of the interaction with the drug, diffraction patterns of SEP did not show changes, whereas VHS patterns evidenced significant changes in some reflections. In particular, reflection corresponding to d (001) of VHS shifted to lower angles after interaction with the drug. The resultant interlayer spaces changed from 12.32 Å in the pristine VHS to 16.05 Å in PZQ-VHS, clearly suggesting the effective inclusion of drug

molecules in the clay mineral interlayer.

3.2. Thermal analysis

The DSC profiles of PZQ showed a strong endothermic peak at 144 °C with enthalpy $\Delta H = -90.41 \text{ Jg}^{-1}$, corresponding to the melting of the (RS)-PZQ crystals (Fig. 2) and with no loss of weight in TGA curve (Fig. 3). Calorimetric profiles of VHS and SEP showed broad endothermic peaks in the range 50–90 °C, corresponding to the evaporation of water. As a result of interaction, DSC curve of PZQ-SEP showed only a very low intensity peak corresponding to water

Fig. 5. FTIR spectra of the studied samples.

evaporation and complete disappearance of melting peak of the drug. In PZQ-VHS curve water evaporation was also evident as well as a small peak corresponding to the melting of the drug, with $\Delta H = 1.86 \text{ Jg}^{-1}$. The crystallinity degree of the drug in the interaction product, calculated as $\Delta H \text{ melting(PZQ/VHS)}/\Delta H \text{ melting(pure PZQ)}$, was approximately 2%. Similar approach was proposed by Cavallaro et al. (2013), studying the amorphization of polyethylene glycol in polymer/clay composites. The obtained results showed that amorphization of the PZQ occurs in the prepared interaction products, justifying the lack of the PZQ reflections in the PZQ-VHS and PZQ-SEP powder XRD patterns. This amorphization is slightly higher in PZQ-SEP product.

Thermogravimetric profiles of the clay minerals showed a weight loss (2% w/w and 10% w/w), corresponding to evaporation of adsorbed water molecules from VHS and SEP surfaces, respectively (Fig. 3). Second weight loss of the sepiolite sample in the interval 250–350 °C corresponded to loss of zeolitic water (Viseras and López-Galindo, 1999). In the interaction products, thermal decomposition of the drug resulted in weight losses in the range between 200 and 400 °C, corroborating the adsorption of the PZQ in these mineral solids.

3.3. Electron microscopy

The microphotographs of the praziquantel (Fig. 4A–B) presented elongated prismatic morphology and crystal sizes $> 100 \mu\text{m}$, similar to those of PZQ racemic mixtures previously observed (Liu et al., 2004; Espinosa-Lara et al., 2013).

SEM microphotographs of montmorillonite (Fig. 4C–D) showed grains with different particle sizes. Particles associated with any impurities were not detected, corroborating the XRD results. In the SEM microphotographs of the PZQ-VHS interaction product, significant changes of texture and morphology were observed (Fig. 4E–F). Filamentous particles of praziquantel were observed between the montmorillonite particles, as well as, the amorphization and the loss of the crystalline structure of praziquantel. The initial PZQ particles disappeared and PZQ formed aggregates in the montmorillonite particles during the dispersion and solvent evaporation process. The amorphization of a portion of the praziquantel and the formation of these small size crystalline fibers may also justify the low crystallinity and the previous lack of XRD reflections in this IP mixture (PZQ-VHS), corroborating XRD diffraction and the DSC results.

Sepiolite morphologies were described previously as being

constituted by grains with different particle sizes formed by fibrous particles (Viseras and López-Galindo, 1999; Suárez and García-Romero, 2012). In PZQ-SEP microphotographs, these well-known characteristics were observable, as well as the absence of crystalline praziquantel, due to the total amorphization of the drug, corroborating the DSC and the XRD results (Fig. 4G–H).

3.4. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

FTIR spectra of the racemic PZQ, sepiolite, montmorillonite and the interaction products (PZQ-VHS and PZQ-SEP) are compared in Fig. 5. PZQ showed two main characteristic bands in the range 2960–2840 cm^{-1} assigned to stretching vibration modes $\nu(\text{CH})$ of CH and CH_2 groups (Rodrigues et al., 2010). Two bands corresponding to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ vibration mode were observed at 1665–1621 cm^{-1} (Rodrigues et al., 2010), which were assigned to each carbonyl group with different local environment in the crystal packing (Borrego-Sánchez et al., 2017). The $\delta(\text{C}=\text{H})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ modes were observed around 1350–1021 cm^{-1} (Passerini et al., 2006). These experimental values coincide with previous theoretical data that completed the infrared spectra of praziquantel, assigning new bands not identified experimentally, both in the molecule (Borrego-Sánchez et al., 2016) and in the crystalline structure of praziquantel (Borrego-Sánchez et al., 2017).

The spectra of montmorillonite and sepiolite showed characteristic bands of the clay minerals at 3700–3600 cm^{-1} of the octahedral OH groups, $\nu(\text{AlOHAl})$, $\nu(\text{AlOHMg})$, $\nu(\text{MgOHMg})$, 1680–1600 cm^{-1} ($\delta(\text{OH water})$) and 1200–1000 cm^{-1} ($\nu(\text{Si}=\text{O})$) (Frost et al., 2001; Ortega-Castro et al., 2009). In PZQ-VHS and PZQ-SEP, the bands of PZQ were detected which means that the drug was present in the interaction product, although no clear differences could be observed due to the high proportion of clays, whose bands overlap those of PZQ.

3.5. In vitro release studies

Drug release profiles of PZQ and the two interaction products are shown in Fig. 6. PZQ dissolution rate was higher in acidic medium (Fig. 6 up) than in intestinal fluid (Fig. 6 down), in concordance with its pH dependent solubility. As it was reported by Chaud et al. (2010), solubility of PZQ was 0.735 mg/mL and 0.454 mg/mL in HCl and phosphate buffer, respectively. Interaction of the drug with the clay

Fig. 6. *In vitro* drug release profiles in HCl 0.001 M. (up) and simulated intestinal fluid (down); (mean values \pm s.d.; n = 6).

minerals induced an increase in dissolution rates with independence of pH. This improvement is particularly important in phosphate buffer (Fig. 6 down), being the intestinal environment the preferential site of absorption of orally administered drugs. The final amount of drug dissolved from the interaction products increased approximately a 20% in simulated intestinal fluid with respect to the pure PZQ. Therefore, PZQ-VHS and PZQ-SEP interaction products might improve oral bio-availability of the drug by increasing both dissolution rate and amount of drug dissolved in FIS.

4. Conclusions

The antihelmintic drug PZQ was easily intercalated in montmorillonite interlayer space and sepiolite channels by using a non-aqueous polar medium (ethanol), which allowed overcoming the water barriers for low-water soluble organic compounds. This method can be extended to any short-chain alcohols where PZQ is soluble. These solvents can be easily eliminated after the preparation process.

PZQ-VHS and PZQ-SEP increased dissolution rates and global amount of drug dissolved. These kinds of interaction products can be

considered as promising alternatives to improve bioavailability of water low-soluble drugs like praziquantel.

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